

STABILITY OF OFFSHORE SLOPES IN SEISMIC REGIONS

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Abstract: The stability of an offshore slope in a seismic area is evaluated using two different procedures: one based on a deterministic approach and the other on a probabilistic approach. From the results of a seismic response analysis, the two procedures are applied for the computation of the permanent displacements induced by the earthquake.

The deterministic procedure is based on a conceptual model consisting of a rigid block on a sloping plane and is developed through double integration of the accelerograms. The probabilistic procedure is based on stochastic models for the definition of peak acceleration and yield acceleration and allows the evaluation of the probabilistic distribution of the permanent displacements.

The results obtained with the two procedures are compared and discussed with reference to a case history.

Sommario: La stabilità di un pendio sottomarino in zona sismica viene valutata con riferimento a due procedure diverse, rispettivamente di tipo deterministico e di tipo probabilistico. A partire dall'analisi di risposta sismica, i due metodi vengono utilizzati per il calcolo delle deformazioni permanenti indotte nel terreno dal sisma.

La procedura di tipo deterministico è basata su un modello di blocco rigido su piano inclinato ed è sviluppata mediante doppia integrazione degli accelerogrammi. La procedura di tipo probabilistico è basata su modelli stocastici per la descrizione di accelerazione di picco e accelerazione di soglia e permette di valutare la distribuzione probabilistica delle deformazioni permanenti.

I risultati ottenuti con le due procedure sono confrontati e discussi con riferimento ad un caso reale.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The assessment of slope stability under seismic conditions is a key design issue in areas characterized by relevant seismicity. This aspect is particularly relevant offshore, where even relatively gentle slopes may be affected by strong motion earthquakes, due to the poor mechanical properties often characterizing the marine sediments.

The stability assessment can be carried out by evaluating the permanent displacements associated with a seismic event by double integration of the acceleration time history, or according to an empirical approach such as the method developed by Lin and Whitman [1]. The empirical approach is suitable for use within a probabilistic framework where the key parameters influencing the slope behaviour are treated as random variables.

In the following discussion, the two methods are applied to the seismic stability analysis of a site located in the Mediterranean Sea, for which a detailed geotechnical characterization is available. The purpose of the study is to illustrate the use of the two methods for design purposes, evaluate the accuracy limitations of the simplified empirical procedure and assess the sensitivity of the basic random parameters influencing the earthquake induced displacements.

2. SLOPE STABILITY ASSESSMENTS IN SEISMIC CONDITIONS

The magnitude of induced slope displacements, rather than considerations on the possibility that the factor of safety drops to unity, should be the criterion for assessing the degree of stability or instability of a slope, during an earthquake [2]. These displacements can be computed by a procedure similar to that used for analyzing the movement of a sliding block on a sloping plane. Such principle has been applied in the past [3] to compute earthquake induced displacements in sand embankments by integrating twice the portion of the acceleration time history that exceeds the critical acceleration a_c (i.e., acceleration value producing a state of limit equilibrium when applied to the block). Sarma [4] presented a simplified procedure where each cycle of the acceleration time history exceeding a_c is given a rectangular, triangular or half sine shape. He found that for a_c/a_{max} greater than 0.5 the triangular pulse is generally appropriate, whereas for a_c/a_{max} values smaller

than 0.5 a rectangular shape is preferable. More recently, based on integration of 86 recorded time histories, Yegian et al. [5] have observed that the triangular shape is generally suitable for a_c/a_{max} greater than 0.1, whereas for a_c/a_{max} smaller than 0.1 all three simple base motions tend to underestimate the displacements.

For seismic stability assessments the acceptable deformation (i.e., the limit between stable and unstable conditions) has to be defined depending on the specific design case. As an example, for a jacket offshore structure founded on sloping seabed the residual displacement must be small enough not to cause structure collapse, and, in particular, the integrity of the foundation piles has to be assured [6].

3. DESCRIPTION OF THE CASE STUDY

The site is located in the Mediterranean Sea and is characterized by a water depth of approximately 100 meters. The slope angle is slightly variable across the area investigated, and a value of 4.5 degrees was selected for the analysis.

The soil properties were defined on the basis of extensive field and laboratory programs. The soil profile consists primarily of normally consolidated clay down to a depth of at least 200 meters. [6]

The shear strength properties were assessed by means of triaxial (UU and CIU), simple shear, torvane and CPT testing. The soil behavior under cyclic loading was investigated by means of cyclic triaxial tests on both granular and cohesive samples.

4. RESPONSE TO SEISMIC EVENTS

A free-field seismic response analysis was carried out to evaluate accelerations, strains and stresses induced in the soil mass by the earthquake [6].

The analysis was conducted using the finite element code QUAD4 [7], where the non linearity of the shear modulus and damping is accounted for by the use of equivalent linear soil properties. Due to the gentle slope of the seabed a one-dimensional finite element model of a 200 meter soil column was used.

A horizontal acceleration time history, obtained from an actual acceleration record scaled to reproduce a peak ground

acceleration of about 0.4 g, was applied at the base of the soil column. The peak ground acceleration value was computed through a seismic risk study of the area for the RIE (Rare Intense Earthquake).

Soil damping and deformability were defined based on available experimental information for sand and clay, and using the relationships developed by Hardin and Drnevich [8].

For the evaluation of permanent displacements, acceleration time histories at several depths were considered. Typical records computed at three significant depths are shown in Figures 1a, 1b and 1c.

Fig. 1: Acceleration time histories computed at the following depths below the mudline: (a) 3.4 m, (b) 18 m, (c) 32 m.

In order to evaluate a proper peak ground acceleration to be used in conjunction with the empirical method, smoothing of the computed records was required to eliminate the effects of spurious high frequencies resulting from the numerical procedure. The response analysis showed that a significant deamplification of the base acceleration takes place within the soil column. The discussion presented herein will concentrate on the potential failure surface located at a depth of 32 meters, which resulted to be the most critical.

5. CRITICAL ACCELERATION

The sliding block model is depicted in Figure 2. The block, located on a sloping plane, tends to move downwards when the acceleration time history along the inclined plane exceeds the critical value $a_c = a_y - a_w$, where a_y is the yield acceleration, related to the shear strength of the soil, and a_w is the acceleration due to the self weight of the soil along the inclined plane.

For an infinite submerged slope in cohesive soil, the critical acceleration value can be inferred from the static factor of safety according to the following relationship:

$$a_c = \frac{\gamma}{\gamma'} \sin \alpha (FS - 1) g \quad (1)$$

where γ' and γ are the buoyant and total soil unit weights, respectively, FS is the static factor of safety, α is the seafloor slope angle, and g is the acceleration due to gravity.

In defining the yield acceleration a_y the shear strength of the soil has to be assessed considering the high strain rate and the cyclic loading conditions associated with a seismic event.

The undrained shear strength of clayey soils tends to increase with the strain rate [9]. For the case study, the cyclic triaxial tests conducted in the laboratory revealed that for a frequency of one hertz the dynamic shear strength of the soil exceeds the static undrained shear strength S_u by a factor of about 1.3. On the other hand, the effects of cyclic loading may lead to strength degradation associated with pore pressure build up, if a limiting strain threshold value is exceeded [10]. Lefebvre et al. [11] presented stress threshold values frequently higher than 50 per cent of the undrained strength obtained at proper strain rates.

For the case study, based on cyclic triaxial tests, an a_y value consistent with the static S_u was selected as adequately conservative for the deterministic analysis. An undrained strength equal to 1.3 times the static S_u value is considered appropriate for the probabilistic approach.

6. DISPLACEMENT COMPUTATION BY NUMERICAL INTEGRATION

The deterministic analysis was carried out assuming the sliding block model depicted in Figure 2 and integrating twice that portion of the acceleration time history that exceeds the critical acceleration value a_c (Figure 3). It was found that the most critical slip plane was located at about 32 meters below mudline where the soil resistance was taken as $S_u=50$ kPa; for this plane a maximum residual displacement of four centimeters was obtained.

Fig. 2: Sliding block model. Fig. 3: Method to compute residual displacement (modified after [3]).

7. DISPLACEMENT PREDICTION BY A SIMPLIFIED MODEL

The procedure developed by Lin and Whitman [1] is based on the deterministic model proposed by Newmark [2], in combination with the ground motion model described by

Vanmarcke [12]. The model by Vanmarcke describes the damaging effect of a seismic excitation by means of four parameters, transforming a non-stationary motion into a normalized Gaussian equivalent stationary motion having a specified duration S:

$$S = \frac{\pi}{\Omega} \exp\left(-\frac{a_{\max}^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (2)$$

where Ω is the dominant circular frequency of the ground acceleration, σ is the root mean square of the acceleration and $a_{\max}$ is the peak of the filtered acceleration at the location of the potential slippage.

Assuming that the excitation is narrow-banded, the expected value of the number of cycles $E[N(S)]$ exceeding the critical acceleration is given by multiplying the duration S by the associated up-crossing rate for a Gaussian excitation.

Based on the assumptions presented above, a relationship providing the expected total displacement has been derived [1]. The formulation includes two empirical functions which were obtained carrying out simulated excitations using 140 acceleration records [1].

For the case study a value of 18 seconds was assigned to the duration of the equivalent stationary motion S, in consideration of the soil type, and of the typical magnitude and epicentral distance of a RIE event [13]. The value of the root mean square of the acceleration σ was then computed based on Eq. (2). The analysis of the response spectrum led to a dominant period of two seconds, and a value of the bandwidth δ equal to 0.5 was estimated.

The analysis was carried out for several values of the critical acceleration and the results are presented in Figure 4. It can be noted that for a_c consistent with the static S_u (50 kPa) the displacement predicted is larger than the value computed by means of the numerical integration. The difference is partly due to the inherent approximation of the simplified method. Furthermore, examining the acceleration time history resulting from the seismic response analysis, it is found that only one peak exceeds the a_c level, as opposed to 3.6 peaks predicted by the model based on the Gaussian assumption. This reveals that the assumed Gaussian ground motion [12] does not fit very well this specific time history.

Fig. 4: Expected displacement vs. undrained shear strength.

Regardless of the accuracy limitations discussed above, the sensitivity analysis presented in Figure 4 indicates the strong influence of S_u , and consequently of a_c , on the expected earthquake induced displacement. As an example, increasing the undrained strength value by 30%, the displacement decreases by almost 90%. Emphasis must be placed on the importance of proper field and laboratory programmes, including static and cyclic soil testing, in order to estimate as accurately as possible the expected value of the critical acceleration.

8. PROBABILITY DISTRIBUTION OF THE ANNUAL EXPECTED PERMANENT DISPLACEMENT

Based on the assumptions associated with the simplified model presented above, the probability distribution of the permanent displacement can be assessed. In general, the following relationship can be written:

$$P(D) = \int P(D|a_c, a_{\max}, \sigma, \Omega, \delta) dF(a_c, a_{\max}, \sigma, \omega_g, \xi_g) \quad (3)$$

where: $P(D|a_c, a_{max}, \sigma, \Omega, \delta)$ is the conditional probability distribution of the permanent displacement, ω_g is the ground natural frequency and ξ_g is the ground damping. Lin and Whitman [1] describe a procedure to evaluate the conditional probability $P(D|a_c, a_{max}, \sigma, \Omega, \delta)$. The joint distribution $F(a_c, a_{max}, \sigma, \omega_g, \xi_g)$ of Eq. (3) can be computed by defining the individual probability distributions of the parameters a_c , a_{max} , σ , ω_g , ξ_g and by considering possible correlations among these parameters. However, the peak ground acceleration and the critical acceleration can be considered as the most influencing random variables.

The statistical distribution of the peak ground acceleration has been assessed through a previous seismic hazard analysis.

The conditional probabilities of exceeding specified displacement values are shown, for displacements up to one meter, in Figure 5.

Fig. 5: Conditional probabilities of exceeding specified displacement values D_0 .

The three curves, which correspond to expected values of a_c consistent with S_u (static), $1.15 S_u$ and $1.3 S_u$, respectively, were obtained on the basis of the conditional probability function presented by Lin and Whitman [1]. The large scatter associated with variable a_c values is clearly visible; as an example, the conditional probability of

exceeding a displacement of 20 cm varies from less than 1% ($1.3 S_u$) to more than 12% (S_u).

The annual probability of exceeding displacement values up to one meter are shown in Figure 6. The plot was obtained considering the return period of the RIE event. The random variables a_c and a_{max} were assumed to follow lognormal distributions [1]. For a_c an expected value consistent with a shear strength equal to $1.3 S_u$ and a coefficient of variation equal to 30% were assumed. Based on Figure 6, it can be observed that the predicted annual probability of exceeding the displacement of four centimeters computed by numerical integration is close to 3×10^{-6} .

Fig. 6: Annual probability of exceeding specified displacement values at a depth of 32 m.

9. CONCLUSIONS

Two different methodologies for the computation of the residual displacements induced in an offshore slope by a seismic event are compared. The first methodology is based on a rigorous, double integration analysis of the acceleration time history. The second relies upon a simplified description of the earthquake, where the ground motion is assumed consistent with a Gaussian distribution.

In light of the discussion presented above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- 1) The characteristics of the ground motion in proximity of the potential failure plane were found to influence considerably the earthquake induced displacement in the slope; therefore a proper seismic response analysis, providing a realistic acceleration time history, is crucial.
- 2) The sensitivity analysis carried out by using the simplified method indicated the key role played by the critical acceleration a_c in controlling the earthquake induced displacement. For the case study an increase of a_c associated with a 30% variation of the soil strength resulted in a reduction of the expected displacement in excess of ten times. Great care should be taken in defining a_c with sufficient accuracy, by means of proper field and laboratory testing programmes.
- 3) The simplified empirical method proved to be simple to use and suitable for preliminary assessments. However, its inherent inaccuracies and poor fitting of the record considered herein resulted in displacement values larger than computed by double integration of the acceleration time history.
- 4) One advantage of the simplified model is the possibility of using it in the framework of a probabilistic approach without major difficulties. An application of the method to determine the annual probability of exceeding the specified displacement value is illustrated herein, with reference to a case study.

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